

**ORGANO-ARSENICALS. PART II. SOME NEW
ARYL AZO-ARSONIC ACIDS ***

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Fourteen aryl azo-arsenic acids, prepared by diazotising *p*-arsanilic acid and coupling with aromatic hydroxy, and amino compounds, as well as sulphonic acids, two by diazotising *o*- and *m*-arsanilic acids and coupling with methone and one by diazotising sulphaniilamide and coupling with *p*-arsanilic acid, have been described.

Protozoal diseases like sleeping sickness have been treated on the one hand with azo dyes like trypan red and on the other, with organo-arsenicals like stoxyl. With a view to combining these two modes of treatment, a number of azo dyes containing arsenic have been synthesised, and patented (Aktien Gesellschaft für Anilin Fabrikation, D.R.P., 212018, 212304, 220063, 216223; Noelting, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1916, *iv*, 19, 361). The two methods employed for the synthesis of azo derivatives of *p*-arsanilic acid are: (a) by the condensation of *p*-nitrosophenylarsonic acid (I) with suitable aryl amines (Karrer, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2065) and (b) by diazotising *p*-arsanilic acid (II) and coupling with suitable components. Condensation of (I) with (II) gives azobenzene-4:4'-diarsonic acid (III) which is a dark powder, easily soluble in alkalis.

Benzene-azo-2:4-tolylenediamino-4'-arsonic acid (VI) is prepared either by coupling the diazonium salt (IV) of *p*-arsanilic acid with *m*-tolylenediamine (V) or by condensing (V) with *p*-nitrosophenylarsonic acid (I) and hydroxylamine (VII)

in alkaline solution (Ehrlich and Bertheim, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 3297; D.R.P., 205449; E.P., 3929 of 1907; Benda, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3878, 3295, 3300).

Barrowcliff, Pymann and Rewfy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1899) have shown that the mono-azo derivatives are only slightly active towards trypanosomes. The azo-arsenic acid (VI) has been found to be more toxic than (III). It has

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been observed that the poly-azo arsenical dyes have a greater trypanocidal action than the mono-azo dyes and are 2.5 times less toxic than atoxyl to the host (cf. Morgan, "Organic Compounds of Arsenic and Antimony", pp. 179-182).

Jacobs and Heidelberger (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1646) and Berlingozzi (*Annal. Chim. Appl.*, 1928, 18, 31, 333) have prepared a number of azo-arsenicals. Quite a number of patents have been taken on azo-arsenicals in general which indicates that this is a fruitful line for further research (cf. Friend, "A Text-Book of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. XI, Part II, p. 231).

In the present investigation fourteen (1 to 14) mono-azo arsenic acids (vide Table I) of the type (VIII), where R stands for the coupling component less one hydrogen atom) have been prepared by method (b) cited above.

Iyer and Chakravarty (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1934, 17A, 41) and Iyer (*ibid.*, 1938, 21A, 65) prepared a number of azo dyes by coupling methone (5 : 5-dimethyldihydroresorcin) with diazonium and tetrazonium salts. All the three aminophenylarsonic acids have now been diazotised and coupled with methone to give compounds (14), (15) and (16) (vide Table I).

TABLE I
"A" stands for arsenic acid.

Compound No	Aryl-azo arsenic acid.	Coupling component.
1.	4-Hydroxy-3-methylazobenzene-4'-A	<i>o</i> -Cresol
2.	4 " " -3- " " 4'-A	<i>m</i> -Cresol
3.	2- " " -5- " " -4'-A	<i>p</i> -Cresol
4.	2 : 4-Dihydroxyazobenzene-4'-A	Resorcinol
5.	2-Hydroxynaphthalene-3-azophenyl-4'-A	β -Naphthol
6.	4-Hydroxy-3-carboxyazobenzene-4'-A	Salicylic acid
7.	4-Amino-3-carboxyazobenzene-4'-A	Anthranilic acid
8.	1-Aminonaphthalene-4-azophenyl-4'-A	α -Naphthylamine
9.	2-Aminonaphthalene-3- " " 4'-A	β -Naphthylamine
10.	2-Hydroxy-3 : 6-disulphonylnaphthyl-azophenyl 4'-A	2-Naphthol-3 : 6-disulphonic acid
11.	1-Amino-3 : 6 : 8-trisulphonyl-2-azophenyl naphthyl-4'-A	8-Aminonaphthalene-1 : 3 : 6-trisulphonic acid
12.	1-Amino-3-hydroxy-3 : 6-disulphonyl-7-azonaphthylphenyl-4'-A	1-Amino-8-hydroxy-naphthalene-3 : 6-disulphonic acid
13.	2-Hydroxy-6 : 8-disulphonyl-7-azonaphthylphenyl-4'-A	2-Naphthol-6 : 8-disulphonic acid
14.	2-Hydroxy-4-dimethyl-6-keto-3 : 4 : 5 : 6-tetrahydroazobenzene-4'-A	Methone
15.	2-Hydroxy-1-dimethyl-6-keto-3 : 4 : 5 : 6-tetrahydroazobenzene-3'-A	"
16.	2-Hydroxy-1-dimethyl-6-keto-3 : 4 : 5 : 6-tetrahydroazobenzene-2'-A	"
17.	4-Sulphonamido-2'-aminoazobenzene-5'-A	<i>p</i> -Aminic acid

When diazotised arsanilic acid is coupled with sulphanilamide in acid medium no product can be isolated. But when sulphanilamide is diazotised and coupled with arsanilic acid, the azo-arsenical (No. 17 of table) separates out neatly.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Compounds (1) to (7), both inclusive and (14) were prepared by diazotising *p*-arsanilic acid and coupling in alkaline medium with the coupling component mentioned against each of them in Table I. Compounds (15) and (16) were prepared by diazotising *m*-amino- and *o*-amino-phenylarsonic acids respectively and coupling with methone. A typical experiment is detailed below.

4-Hydroxy-3-methylazobenzene-4'-arsonic Acid, (1).—Arsanilic acid (4.32 g.) dissolved in 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (14 c. c.) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (1.4 g.) dissolved in water (14 c.c.) The clear diazonium solution was then poured into *o*-cresol (2.16 g.) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (40 c.c.). The dark coloured solution thus obtained was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when an orange dye separated. It was filtered and washed with water. It is soluble in hot alcohol, slightly soluble in acetic acid, insoluble in water and ether. It was crystallised from alcohol, yield 4.5 g.

Compounds (8) and (9) were prepared according to the details given below using α - and β -naphthylamines respectively.

1-Aminonaphthalene-4-azophenyl-4'-arsonic Acid, (8).—The diazonium solution from arsanilic acid (2.17 g.) was added under stirring to a well cooled solution of α -naphthylamine (1.43 g.) in alcohol (50 c. c.) when an intensely coloured solution resulted. On adding an equal volume of water and leaving it overnight the dye was thrown out as a dark precipitate. It was filtered, washed with water and dried. It is soluble in acids, alkalis and alcohol, insoluble in water, yield 3.5 g.

Compounds (10), (11), (12) and (13) were obtained by coupling diazotised *p*-arsanilic acid with the respective sulphonic acid in alkaline medium and isolating the product as in the typical experiment detailed below.

2-Hydroxy-3 : 6-disulphonylnaphthylazophenyl-4'-arsonic Acid, (10).—The diazonium solution from arsanilic acid (2.17 g.) was slowly added with stirring to a well cooled solution of 2 naphthol-3 : 6-disulphonic acid* (3 g.) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (60 c. c.). The resulting solution was acidified and poured into excess of alcohol when the dye was thrown out as an orange-red precipitate. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. It is soluble in alkalis, carbonates and water; insoluble in alcohol, yield 2.7 g.

4-Sulphonamido-2-aminoazobenzene-5'-arsonic Acid, (17).—Sulphanilamide (1.7 g.) dissolved in 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (8 c. c.) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.7 g.) in water (7 c. c.) and coupled with arsanilic acid (2.2 g.) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (30 c. c.). After acidification and standing overnight, a red dye separated which was filtered, washed with water and dried, yield 2.3 g.

All the compounds, obtained in good yield, were purified either by crystallisation from alcohol or acetic acid or by dissolution in alkali and precipitation by acid. They had no melting point. The analytical data, excepting for compound (12), which could not be obtained pure enough for analysis, are given in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Formula.	% Arsenic		No.	Formula.	% Arsenic	
		Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_2As$	22.09	22.32	9.	$C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2As$	20.10	20.21
2.	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_2As$	22.19	22.32	10.	$C_{16}H_{13}O_{10}N_2S_2As$	14.03	14.10
3.	$C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_2As$	22.19	22.32	11.	$C_{16}H_{13}O_{10}N_2S_2As$	12.16	12.27
4.	$C_{12}H_{11}O_6N_2As$	21.97	22.13	12.	Not analysed		
5.	$C_{16}H_{13}O_4N_2As$	20.00	20.17	13.	$C_{16}H_{13}O_{10}N_2S_2As$	13.95	14.10
6.	$C_{13}H_{11}O_6N_2As$	20.31	20.46	14.	$C_{14}H_{17}O_6N_2As$	20.31	20.38
7.	$C_{13}H_{12}O_6N_2As$	20.46	20.55	15.	..	20.31	20.38
8.	$C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2As$	19.99	20.21	16.	..	20.32	20.38
				17.	$C_{16}H_{13}O_6N_2S_2As$	18.69	18.75

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